

INNOVATIVE WAYS TO DEVELOP EDUCATIONAL PROCESSES IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS AND ITS PROSPECTS

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Annotation. This article offers and recommendations on pedagogical methods, methods and innovative ways of developing education in a preschool educational organization. There are also scientific-theoretical analyses of the prospects for the development strategy of Education.

Keywords: education, state curriculum "first step", pedagogical activity, strategic development.

In the preschool organization, education, especially training, is carried out mainly in the form of various games. Therefore, it is important to observe and analyze the activities of the game by the director. This is due to the fact that this variety of games has a special place in the formation of the personality of a preschool child, the variety of types of games and their characteristic of finding and developing positive qualities in educators. It requires the director to be well aware of all game-specific features, to conduct an in-depth analysis of the gameplay and to provide timely assistance to educators. As noted, children's games are distinguished by their variety. They change and improve during the entire period of the child's stay in the preschool organization, according to the nature of the manifestation of content, organization, educational activity and opportunities, the effect they exert on children.

The director should pay special attention to the choice of game types. In particular, to what extent the director uses games that serve to form the language, worldview, qualities and qualities of the child in the activities carried out by the educator, to develop his creative capabilities, for example, interest in music or painting, to what extent their suitability for educational goals and objectives should be analyzed and, if necessary, rely on his knowledge and experience, give the It is necessary to develop a system of games of different age groups on the basis of the state program "first step" and draw up a schedule for monitoring the gameplay. It is a pity that the director attaches special importance to the fact that in all groups the necessary conditions are created for

conducting games-based activities (sufficient time is allocated for games, the presence of a place for conducting them full-fledged and interesting, the presence of toys, scarecrows and guides, and the correct placement in rooms, etc.).

Thus, the leadership activity of the director in this regard should be integrated into the development of the child's speech, physical and mental activity by promoting the effective and rational use of methods and methods that serve the upbringing of the upbringing of the upbringing, ensuring the stability of their emotional-mental state, including, if necessary, prolonging and complicating play activities.

The following can be included in the factors that contribute to the full and interesting conduct of games in groups:

- a) that the educator has the ability to make the game full-fledged and interesting, as well as manage it wisely;
- b) the creation of the appropriate environment and conditions for a full-fledged and interesting organization of the game;
- v) the fact that the training included in the agenda plan provides enough time for the game.

It is known that the behavior of children in the process of play is clearly visible in their desire to imitate adult people. Therefore, in the process of education and training carried out in a preschool educational organization, it is necessary to take into account this aspect, strive to develop through the game from physical, mental, spiritual JIAT, to form their interests and creative capabilities.

In the activities of the director, in addition to the above-mentioned factors, a comparative examination also occupies an important place. Its importance is manifested in comparing, analyzing and evaluating the pedagogical activity of the educator with the work experience of another educator (for example, comparing the work activities of Educators of side groups).

Comparative examination in the study of the implementation of certain sections of the program, it is advisable to apply in the analysis of the knowledge, skills and qualifications of various educators and the effectiveness of work in general. The results of the comparative analysis can be discussed at the Supervisory Board. A comparative examination can be carried out in the form of access to groups and direct observation of the work of caregivers, analysis of plans, children's work and other documents. The director analyzes daily pedagogical processes, studies and training, the activities of educators, the

quality of the knowledge and skills they receive along with educators, seeks innovative ways to improve the educational process, improve their effectiveness. Comparative examination helps to increase the popularity of advanced work experience, the educational process and the level of universal potential of all group Educators. Regardless of the application of any type of control, it can be given the expected effect only when the director is seriously, carefully prepared.

First of all, the purpose of the examination should be clearly defined (for example, in small groups, appropriate conditions have been created for the variety of activities of children during the day;

observation of the interaction of those brought up in large groups in the process of play and labor, in particular, their harmony during play or in the process of Labor.

In the Middle groups, however, the director checks the extent to which the program for raising the speech of educators is being mastered, the degree of formation of speech activity and skills of children. Having clearly determined the purpose of the comparative examination, the director compares the educational and educational work plan of the educator with the requirements of the state curriculum "first step". Get acquainted with the results of the previous examination, study the work of children, talk to the educator and toddlers. It is also necessary to familiarize yourself with new methodological literature and developments, conclusions of generalizations of advanced pedagogical experience, the results of scientific research and develop a concise plan of examination, referring to the questions that you want to identify in the verification process.

In improving the quality of education in preschool educational organizations in 2023-2026, the director of the preschool educational organization is envisaged to carry out the following innovative work:

1. The pedagogical Council of the preschool educational organization, the general production meeting, the general parents meeting, the laws and orders of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan regarding the preschool education system. Decisions of the Cabinet of ministers to deliver the essence of the content to the general public of legal and regulatory documents of the ministry and Related Agencies.

2. On the basis of the state educational program" the first step", each child is approached individually as a person, developing the interests of the child

in the Centers of activity and creating conditions for the manifestation of his creativity.

3. Holding an open day on the topic “The Book is our friend” twice a year in order to arouse interest in the book in every child from an early age.

4. Further improvement of the activities of the Supervisory Board, established in the preschool organization, and the permanent establishment of communication with parents.

5. 5 important initiatives of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan, identifying the abilities of children in 5 important areas, ensuring the participation of the district and municipal competitions.

6. Preschool education to ensure that the pedagogical workers of the organization regularly perform in the media of educational activities processes, screening contests, open days and festive evenings.

7. Participation in seminars held in the district and city and ensuring the participation of pedagogical staff.

8. Creating conditions for excellent learning of the Russian language and English language of Educators of the preschool educational organization.

9. About the Innovative School named after Moses al Khwarezmiy preschool educational organization to interest a large group of educators.

10. Giving insights into the president's school to preschool children.

In conclusion, the qualitative preparation of schoolchildren for school education, constantly developing the work carried out in the field of preschool education, is a strategic task of state preschool educational organizations.

In the education and formation of preschoolers as representatives of the spiritual bakamol generation, it is extremely important to teach the basics of modern value science, which is a complex of knowledge about the sense of knowledge and knowledge, the category of educational values, the manifestations of their essence, content. For this reason, the generalized areas of knowledge of the achievements of the umuninsonian in relation to the standards of retribution, the use of opportunity is one of the main criteria for the effectiveness of Education.

In this regard, it is in accordance with the proverb that these values are instilled in the minds of children by organizing spiritual and educational activities in every activity in preschool educational organizations, through Proverbs, fairy tales, poems from folk oral creativity.

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